

Chemical Constituents of the Leaves of *Clerodendron colebrookianum*, Walp., a Potent Hypotensive Plant

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The genus *Clerodendron* (Verbenaceae) has been the subjects of numerous investigations for its medicinal value^{1,2} and novel chemical properties. The genus provides the novel diterpenoid related to clerodin^{2,3}. In consideration of the importance of the genus from medicinal and chemical stand-point we undertook examination of *C. colebrookianum*, and report our results.

The air-dried finely powdered leaves (4 kg) were extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) in a Soxhlet apparatus for 4 weeks. The concentrated (*in vacuo*) extract on chromatography over silica gel (60–120 mesh, E. Merck; eluant : petrol) afforded a colourless solid, C₃₀H₆₂, (*M*⁺ 422), m.p. 62° (benzene) and was identified as triacontane from spectral data. The petrol-benzene fraction (4 : 1) of the above column yielded an aliphatic alcohol, C₂₈H₅₆O, (*M*⁺ 410), m.p. 84°. This compound showed the presence of a hydroxyl function at ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 450 (OH), 2 914, 2 880 (–CH₂–), 1 138, 1 050, 720 and 705 cm⁻¹. The identity of the compound was confirmed by ¹H nmr data⁴ and mass fragmentation pattern⁴ as octacosanol. Elution with a mixture of petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 2) afforded a solid, C₂₉H₄₆O, (*M*⁺ 410), m.p. 143–44°, acetate, m.p. 140°, which was identified as (24s)ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3 β -ol⁵ from its spectral data.

Further elution with a mixture of benzene-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) afforded a white solid which was a mixture of two closely related compounds, and these were separated to two compounds A and B by repeated chromatography and crystallisation. Compound A, C₁₆H₃₂O₂, (*M*⁺ 256), m.p. 62° and compound B, (*M*⁺ 284), m.p. 70°, were acidic to

litmus. Both the compounds showed almost identical ir bands at ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 300–3 100 (OH), 2 910, 2 850 (–CH₂–), 1 705 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1 463 (C–O–H, band), 940 (–O–H, out-of-plane bend), 721 cm⁻¹. Compounds A and B were identified as palmitic and stearic acid respectively, from its ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data.

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